

Nanostructured ZnO coatings as antiviral surfaces: Influence of synthesis methodology on photocatalytic efficiency

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ABSTRACT

The development of antiviral coatings is crucial for mitigating pathogen transmission. This study evaluates the influence of fabrication methods on the structural, optical, and antiviral properties of nanostructured (NSs) ZnO thin-film coatings for MS2 bacteriophage inactivation under ambient white light (~1000 lux). The quality and morphology of ZnO nanostructures prepared *via* solution-based methods (sol-gel and hydrothermal) and aerosol-assisted chemical vapour deposition (AACVD) were compared. Structural and optical analyses revealed that AACVD produced highly crystalline, homogeneous ZnO film coatings with well-oriented [001] growth, while solution-based methods resulted in partial amorphous characteristics and bandgap blue shift due to carbon contamination. Antiviral tests showed that AACVD ZnO film coatings achieved a 4-log reduction (99.99 %) in MS2 infectivity within 2 h, outperforming the 2-log reduction achieved by solution-based coatings. These results underscore AACVD as a scalable and efficient method for fabricating high-performance ZnO-based antiviral coatings.

1. Introduction

Zinc oxide (ZnO) is considered one of the most versatile metal oxides due to its chemical stability and optoelectronic properties. At ambient conditions, it adopts the hexagonal wurtzite structure [1], with a non-centrosymmetric polar unit cell that can favour growth in different directions depending on synthesis conditions. This enables easy preparation of nanostructures (NSs), which are characterised by having one dimension below 100 nm, in a wide variety of nanosized morphologies [2] with properties different from those of their bulk counterparts [3]. Generally, ZnO NSs can be prepared from virtually inexpensive precursors, so ZnO-based devices can be produced cost-effectively. As a result, throughout the last decade, ZnO NSs have emerged as a potential and competitive candidate in commercial markets, becoming the third most used metal-containing nanomaterial [4].

The low cost and toxicity of this metal oxide offer a large palette of possible applications, of which antimicrobial uses are well known [5]. These uses are related to the specific electronic structure of ZnO, which results in good photocatalytic performance [6]. Its enhanced oxidative stress caused by photo-induced reactive oxygen species (ROS)

generation can damage viral envelopes [7,8]. Additionally, Zn²⁺ ions are leached from ZnO in both acidic and basic aqueous solutions [9,10], which have been shown to penetrate cell walls impairing virus replication even at concentrations low enough that are biologically safe for humans [11]. A manyfold increase in surface area of NS materials greatly increases antimicrobial activity, and nanosized ZnO has been proven effective not only against bacteria and fungi but also viruses [11–13]. However, care must be taken as concerns arise related to potential adverse cellular responses resulting from metal leaching for application in solution [14].

Cytotoxic antiviral effects of ZnO NSs strongly depend on their surface charge and size [7], being more pronounced in elongated ones, *i.e.* nanorods (NRs) [8]. Still, their application to eliminate pathogenic species in air, liquids, or touch surfaces is relatively novel [6], but has already garnered significant interest due to its biocompatibility, high degree of toxic selectivity against pathogens, and simultaneous safety for humans [15].

Another significant benefit of ZnO NSs is that they can be prepared through a wide variety of methods [16]. While green synthesis methods are gaining attention due to their clear advantages in terms of using

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recyclable sources and low toxicity solvents, their limited reproducibility and unpredictable scalability are still big limiting factors [17]. Generally, vapour-phase physical methods can produce ZnO NSs of excellent crystalline quality at the expense of high cost and production time [18]. In turn, chemical methods are more versatile and cost-effective, and can produce materials at a higher rate. This is because their solution-based nature widens the range of combinations of molecular precursors, solvents and surfactants, incrementing the possibilities for morphological features of the resulting NSs [19]. Currently, the most popular and developed chemical methods to produce metal oxide NSs are sol-gel and hydrothermal syntheses, which can offer high reproducibility, reduced production cost and easy scalability. However, they have been mostly optimised to produce free-standing nanoparticle materials which pose a potential toxicity issue in aqueous solution, as Zn^{2+} ion leaching and recovery of nanoparticle photocatalysts are challenging issues [20,21]. At present, reports on toxicity of nanoparticle materials for bacteria [22], mice [23], and even humans [24] are growing, linked to oxidative stress of cell membranes, DNA and proteins. Antiviral applications are mainly relevant for touch surfaces, for which ZnO NSs should be prepared robustly adhered to substrates as NRs to have a practical use [25–27]. For this application Zn^{2+} leaching should not be an issue, as the material is not submerged in solution.

Fabrication of thin films of NRs typically requires the use of either a crystalline template or a ZnO textured seed layer to promote crystal growth perpendicular to the substrate [28]. While crystalline substrates are generally costly and/or opaque, seed layers can be easily prepared through simple, inexpensive, and highly reproducible synthesis approaches [29]. One common option is through dip-coating, where surfactants facilitate structure relaxation during sintering that favours texturing; another common option is seeding through drop-casting, in which fast solvent removal favours crystallite nucleation through island growth. Both seeding methods require a sintering step to remove organic by-products and form crystalline seeds [30], and then NRs can grow over them through oriented attachment, *i.e.* through forced crystal growth along the polar (00 *n*) crystallographic directions, which is referred to as *c*-axis preferential growth. The driving force behind this 1-dimensional growth is that the alignment of planes eliminates high-energy facets forming longitudinal structures, therefore reducing the surface energy and the overall free energy of the system [31]. Sol-gel and hydrothermal synthesis are well-established methods to prepare ZnO NRs through the use of organometallic reagents or inorganic salts – *e.g.* $Zn(acac)_2$, $Zn(OAc)_2$, $Zn(NO_3)_2$ and $ZnCl_2$ – and the typical surfactants (amines), as well as polar solvents favour longitudinal growth [6,17,18]. That is because amines adhere to negatively charged non-polar laterally exposed planes of ZnO NRs suppressing lateral growth, and polar solvents favour growth toward polar directions [19]. It must be noted that although the use of surfactants can increase texturing and crystallisation rate, they often have limited stability in the presence of ZnO precursors, and their decomposition products can affect film properties [32]. Achieving full crystallinity in either method can take several hours, and subsequent drying or calcination steps may be needed to get rid of any remaining organic residue from precursor or surfactant decomposition during synthesis [2,6,16,28]. In addition, these methodologies leave a leftover solution containing excess unreacted precursor, surfactants and reaction byproducts, which need appropriate recovery and treatment.

Alternatively, the solution-to-vapour-adapted technique aerosol-assisted chemical vapour deposition (AACVD) retains the advantages of solvent-based synthesis [33,34]. Moreover, precise control of precursor/solvent supersaturation enables the synthesis of NRs coatings without seed layers or crystallographic templates, eliminating the need for drying or sintering steps. This simplifies the process while minimising surface reconstruction effects [34]. In an AACVD process, an aerosol mist containing the precursor is transported to the reaction chamber, where thermal activation drives gas-phase reactions in a solvent-free environment. Surfactants and by-products are removed through the exhaust gas, passing through a scrubber solution if

necessary, and yielding highly pure and crystalline ZnO coatings at a high deposition rate [35]. Additionally, the use of AACVD allows NSs coatings to be deposited on amorphous substrates [36], which is not feasible with standard CVD methods [37].

In this study, we employed three solvent-based techniques to produce ZnO NRs film coatings. We investigated the influence of synthesis conditions on their structural and optical properties and their correlation with antiviral performance. The photocatalytic efficiency of these materials was assessed through the degradation of MS2 phage (ATCC 15597B1) under white light irradiation, revealing a strong dependence on synthesis methodology. The highest-quality ZnO NRs achieved complete inactivation of the phage within 2 h of light exposure.

2. Experimental section

Zinc acetate dihydrate (ZAD, $Zn(O_2CCH_3)_2 \cdot 2 H_2O$, 99.9 %), 2-aminoethanol (AE, C_2H_7NO , 99 %), and 2-methoxyethanol (ME, $C_3H_8O_2$, 99.5 %) were used to produce the ZnO seed layer coatings as per literature [32,37]. Zinc nitrate hexahydrate (ZNH, $Zn(NO_3)_2 \cdot 6 H_2O$), and hexamethylenetetramine (HMTA, $C_6H_{12}N_4$) were used to produce ZnO NRs film coatings through sol-gel and hydrothermal methodology. Zinc chloride ($ZnCl_2$, ≥ 98 %), ethanol (EtOH, 99 %), methanol (MeOH, 99 %), acetone (Me_2CO , 99 %), and 2-propanol (IPA, 99.9 %) were used to develop ZnO NRs film coatings via AACVD process [36]. All films were grown on float glass substrates pre-coated with a SiO_2 barrier layer to prevent ion diffusion from the glass into the film. Substrates were thoroughly cleaned using acetone and 2-propanol, and distilled water, then dried in air prior to use. *Escherichia coli* bacteriophage MS2-15597-B1 (ATCC) was used to perform the antiviral photocatalytic tests.

2.1. Synthesis of ZnO NRs via wet chemical processes sol-gel and hydrothermal

The combined use of two seeding methods – dip-coating and drop-casting – and two methods to grow NRs have been investigated in this work. In the dip-coating method, the coated glass is immersed in a seeding precursor solution of ZAD dissolved in a mixture of AE and ME at room temperature with ZAD:ME molar ratio of 1 (0.75 M ZAD) [38]. The solution was magnetically stirred for 30 min until clear, and borosilicate glass substrates (2.5 × 2.5 cm) were dipped, withdrawn at 6 $cm \cdot min^{-1}$, and coated in 1–5 times to ensure uniform coverage of the seed layer over the substrate. Excess solvent was removed in two steps, first drying at 300 °C for 10 min, followed by annealing at 500 °C for 1 h (Fig. 1a, top).

For the drop-casting method, a precursor solution (0.001–0.03 M) of ZAD in EtOH was used following a report from Greene *et al* [39]. The solution was drop-casted using a Pasteur pipette until surface saturation, left for 15 s, and then washed with absolute EtOH. This process was repeated 15 times to ensure complete and uniform coverage, followed by annealing at 350 °C for 1 h in a muffle furnace. In this approach, supersaturation of ZAD solutions led to ZnO seeding from protonuclei with no preferential orientation, with texturing induced through annealing at an optimal temperature to promote *c*-axis orientation while preventing surfactant contamination (Fig. 1a, bottom).

Following the seeding processes, ZnO NRs film coatings were grown on the seeded substrates using sol-gel and hydrothermal methods. Both methods utilise ZNH and HMTA as chemical precursors, which react under high temperatures to produce ZnO, as described by Eq. 1:

The aqueous precursor solutions were prepared by the dropwise addition of a 20 mM ZNH solution into a 20 mM HMTA solution under vigorous stirring (25 mM). ZnO-seeded borosilicate slides were then

Fig. 1. (a) Schematic representation of the dip-coating (top) and drop-casting (bottom) processes employed to prepare the seed layer and (b) scheme of NRs growth on the seed layer from sol-gel (top) and hydrothermal (bottom) methods employed in this work.

immersed in each solution in either an upward or downward orientation. For sol-gel synthesis, NRs thin films were grown at 95 °C for 5 h under atmospheric pressure (Fig. 1b, top). Alternatively, for hydrothermal synthesis, growth was carried out at 90 °C for 2.5 h in a Teflon-lined stainless-steel sealed autoclave (Fig. 1b, bottom). After synthesis, ZnO NRs thin films were dried and annealed at 400 °C in a muffle furnace to maximise purity and crystallinity. Optimal substrate coverage and nanostructured formation were achieved using an extraction rate of 6 cm·min⁻¹ for dip-coating and 0.03 M precursor solution for drop-casting. Further details of the synthesis conditions are provided in Table S1.

2.2. Synthesis of ZnO NRs via aerosol-assisted chemical vapour deposition (AACVD)

ZnO NRs thin films were synthesised by controlling precursor/solvent supersaturation to prevent the formation of nonadherent powders or polycrystalline thin films, enabling the growth of columnar structures without ZnO catalyst seed layers. Precursor solutions for AACVD were prepared dissolving ZnCl₂ in different polar solvents, including EtOH, IPA, MeOH and Me₂O at concentrations ranging 0.04–0.4 M. The precursor salt (1–10 mmol) was dissolved in 25 mL aliquots of each solvent using ultrasonic agitation for 20 min. The synthesis of ZnO NRs film coatings was performed in an AACVD reactor consisting of a graphite block (170 × 60 mm) housed within a quartz glass tube and heated by an

embedded *Whatman* heater cartridge (Fig. 2). Temperature control was achieved using Pt-Rh thermocouples. The precursor solution was placed in a glass bubbler, where an aerosol mist was generated using an ultrasonic liquid atomiser (LIQUIFOG, Johnson Matthey) and transported into the reaction chamber using N₂ gas (99.9 %, Air Liquid). N₂ flow rates ranging from 2 to 5 L·min⁻¹ were used to optimise the deposition of uniform film coatings on the glass substrate. A NaOH_{aq} scrubber was connected to the exhaust to neutralise Cl-containing byproducts as aqueous NaCl. Silica-coated barrier glass was used as the substrate to prevent unwanted ion leaching. ZnO NRs film coatings were deposited at 400 °C for 20–50 min, yielding adherent, uniform, greyish coatings with good surface coverage. A summary of the AACVD-synthesised is provided in Table S2.

2.3. Analytical methods

The crystallinity, morphology, and optical properties of the as-synthesised ZnO NRs film coatings were characterised using X-ray diffraction (XRD), scanning electron microscopy (SEM) and UV-Vis-NIR spectroscopy. XRD analyses were performed using a X'Pert PRO diffractometer, operating with monochromated Cu x-ray source (K_α, 1.54 Å). Coatings were analysed at a glancing incident angle (θ) of 1°, and diffraction patterns were collected over the 20–60° range with a step size of 0.05° and a step time of 2 s per point. UV-Visible spectroscopy was performed using a double monochromated Cary 5000 UV-Vis-NIR

Fig. 2. Schematic representation of the AACVD process to grow ZnO NRs thin films employed in this work. The precursor solution is carried as an aerosol to the heated amorphous substrate, where growth of *c*-oriented structures occurs without seeding. A scrubber is attached to the exhaust to capture unreacted species or byproducts of the reaction.

spectrophotometer in the 300–1200 nm range. The surface morphology of all coatings was evaluated from images collected using a JEOL JSM 7600 F Field Emission SEM at an accelerating voltage of 5 kV. The content of Zn^{2+} ions was measured with an Inductively Coupled Plasma-Optical Emission Spectrometer using an ICP-OES 5800 Agilent.

2.4. Photocatalytic testing

The antiviral properties of $1 \times 1 \text{ cm}^2$ borosilicate squares, both uncoated (control) and ZnO coated with NRs film coatings, was evaluated against the MS2 bacteriophage (ATCC 15597B1) under white light illumination (1000 lux, Philips Master TL5 HE 14 W/865) from a fluorescent tube. MS2, a model virus similar to other waterborne viruses, was selected due to its low pathogenicity and ease of propagation. Stock solutions of the phage were prepared in Tryptone Yeast Glucose (TYG) medium, while the host bacteria *E. coli*, was cultured at 37 °C for 6 h. The phage stock was diluted to obtain an inoculum of $\sim 10^5$ of plaque-forming units (PFU) per mL. All ZnO NRs-coated and control samples were inoculated with 25 μL of the MS2 stock ($\sim 10^5 \text{ PFU}\cdot\text{mL}^{-1}$), placed in Petri dishes, and irradiated with a standard ceiling fluorescent lamp (1000 lux) for a 2 h period. To verify the inoculum concentration, 10-fold serial dilutions were plated on agar for viable counts before exposure.

For testing, a 25 μL droplet of MS2 suspension ($\sim 1 \times 10^5 \text{ PFU}\cdot\text{mL}^{-1}$) was placed at the centre of each sample ($1 \times 1 \text{ cm}^2$) and immediately covered with a sterile microscope cover glass of the same dimensions to prevent evaporation. Samples were irradiated with a ceiling-mounted fluorescent lamp (1000 lux) for 2 h, following ISO 18071:2016 guidelines for antiviral self-cleaning surfaces. After illumination, samples were rinsed with 450 μL of phosphate-buffer solution (PBS) and vortexed for 15 s to recover the viral suspension. The recovered suspensions and their 10-fold serial dilutions were plated with semi-solid TYG agar and incubated at 37 °C for 24 h for plaque enumeration. All experiments were performed in triplicate to ensure reproducibility. Further details of the photocatalytic test procedure are provided in the [Supporting Information](#).

3. Results and discussion

3.1. Structural analysis. Film morphology and crystallography

3.1.1. NSs coatings prepared via wet-chemical processes

Characterisation of the seeding layers using GIXRD and SEM was not feasible due to their low substrate coverage and minimal thickness. Diffraction patterns would display noise from the borosilicate substrate, while SEM imaging would be hindered by surface charging effects from the high resistivity of the substrate. Additionally, applying a conductive gold topcoat of sufficient thickness to mitigate charging could mask the morphology of the seeding layer. Therefore, the quality of the seeding layers was inferred from the final morphology of NSs films.

3.1.1.1. Dip-coating. During the dip-coating step, the precursor reacts with the mixture of amine surfactant (AE) and a polar solvent (ME) forming a stable chelated Zn^{2+} tetrameric intermediate that decomposes forcing preferential *c*-axis orientation, as the chelated intermediate develops into ZnO nuclei preferentially towards the (002) minimum-surface-energy [32]. Indeed, longitudinal NS formation was observed in all samples, confirming that *c*-axis texturing was promoted in ZnO seed layers. In samples prepared by sol-gel, a low number of dipping steps resulted in the formation of wide, hexagonal ZnO rods ($\sim 2 \mu\text{m}$ wide) arranged in a highly dispersed and inhomogeneous manner. Increasing the number of dipping steps led to thinner (500 nm) vertically aligned rods but also increased agglomeration (Fig. 3a-c). The number of seeding steps had minimal impact on coatings prepared via hydrothermal synthesis, as thin NRs grew uniformly across all samples due to the inherent synthesis conditions of the hydrothermal process (Fig. 3d). Although NRs (60 nm in diameter) with strong *c*-axis preferential growth were obtained from dip-coated seed layers, as confirmed by GIXRD (Fig. 3g), both sol-gel (Fig. 3e) and hydrothermal (Fig. 3f) samples exhibited uneven coverage and the presence of tentacle-like structures. This irregularity is likely attributed to drying inhomogeneities during dip-coating [40], where uneven solvent evaporation from surface droplets generates localised nucleation points of agglomerated seeds (inset of Fig. 3f). Given the resulting uneven coverage, this method is unsuitable as a scalable seeding approach.

3.1.1.2. Drop-casting. This seeding approach resulted in more homogeneous substrate coverage, eliminating morphological irregularities associated with uneven droplet evaporation. The seeding parameters significantly influenced the morphology of the rods in film coatings prepared via sol-gel, although preferential *c*-axis growth was generally observed. At low precursor concentrations, small ($\sim 40 \text{ nm}$ wide) but poorly defined NRs were formed, while increasing the concentration led to the development of short hexagonal blocks ($\sim 170 \text{ nm}$ wide) and eventually flower-like structures, none of which exhibited a defined NR-type morphology within the tested ZAD concentration range (Fig. 4a-c). In contrast, coatings produced via hydrothermal synthesis consistently exhibited well-defined NRs formation across all ZAD concentrations. Variations in seed precursor concentration only induced minor morphological changes, establishing drop-casting seeding followed by hydrothermal growth as a promising and potentially scalable approach. Seeding layers prepared with precursor concentration up to 0.15 M produced dense arrays of thin NRs ($\sim 60 \text{ nm}$ wide), indicative of uniform ZnO seed nucleation (Fig. 4d). At higher precursor concentrations, the coatings consisted of a mixture of thin ($\sim 74 \text{ nm}$ wide) and wider ($\sim 260 \text{ nm}$ wide) rods (Fig. 4e). GIXRD patterns confirmed the presence of crystalline ZnO with pronounced *c*-axis preferential growth in samples featuring well-defined rod-shaped nanostructures (Fig. 4f). The consistency between SEM and GIXRD data was evident, as films with poor coverage exhibited low signal-to-noise ratios (Fig. 4b), while flower-like structures limited [001] preferential growth (Fig. 4c).

These findings suggest that size, density, and distribution strongly

Fig. 3. ZnO structured coatings prepared from dip-coated seeded layers in which nanostructures are grown through sol-gel after dip-coating (a) 1 time, (b) 3 times and (c) 5 times, and (d) hydrothermal processes after dip-coating 3 times. Tentacle-like inhomogeneities on these coatings observed for samples obtained from (e) sol-gel and (f) hydrothermal syntheses. (g) Normalised GIXRD patterns of samples a-d showing preferential c-axis orientation compared to the ZnO powder standard (JCPDS No. 36-1451).

Fig. 4. ZnO structured coatings prepared from drop-casted seeded layers in which nanostructures are grown through (a)-(c) sol-gel and (d)-(e) hydrothermal processes. (f) Normalised GIXRD patterns of samples a-e showing preferential c-axis orientation compared to the ZnO powder standard (JCPDS No. 36-1451).

depend on the seeding method, directly impacting the characteristics of the resulting ZnO structured film coatings. The wide range of tuneable parameters in solvent-based methodologies allows for the promotion of c-axis growth but also influences substrate coverage and homogeneity. Regarding rod growth, the sol-gel method demonstrated a strong dependence on seeding parameters and did not reliably produce NRs, whereas hydrothermal synthesis proved more suitable for generating NRs coatings, thereby offering larger surface areas, uniform coverage, and high reproducibility.

3.1.2. NSs coatings prepared via aerosol-assisted chemical vapour deposition

ZnO coatings with different structures were obtained depending on the choice of solvent and precursor solution concentration. However, preferential columnar growth was exclusively observed in alcohols

containing β -hydrogen atoms (Fig. 5a-d), suggesting that rod-shaped formation proceeds via a metastable intermediate [41]. Additionally, EtOH is known to increase the energy between adatoms and the substrate, thereby inhibiting ZnO growth parallel to the surface in favour of columnar orientation [36]. Coatings synthesised from ethanolic precursor solutions at low ZnCl_2 concentrations exhibited homogeneous yet incomplete surface coverage. Increasing the precursor concentration up to 0.2 M resulted in improved coverage and enhanced NR formation (Fig. 5a). Beyond this threshold, denser films composed of progressively wider rods were obtained, eventually leading to rod coalescence and a reduction in total surface area. Optimally grown NRs displayed uniform length and diameter distributions. Notably, although their widths ranged from 100 to 150 nm at the base, these NRs feature pencil- or blade-like tips in contrast to previously observed flat hexagonal capping, with tip diameters ranging from 20 to 60 nm. Such morphology is

Fig. 5. Top-view SEM of ZnO NSs coatings prepared using AACVD of precursor solutions in EtOH with ZnCl₂ concentrations (a) 0.04 M, (b) 0.1 M and (c) 0.2 M as well as coatings prepared via AACVD from 0.2 M solutions of (d) IPA, (e) MeOH and (f) Me₂CO. All films are prepared at 400 °C for 20 min. (g) Normalised GIXRD patterns of samples a-f showing variable preferential orientation compared to the ZnO powder standard (JCPDS No. 36–1451).

characteristic of rapid precursor depletion at the final growth stage, a phenomenon commonly observed in vapour-phase synthesis of nanostructures [40]. In contrast, coatings derived from MeOH and Me₂CO (Fig. 5e and f) exhibited poorly defined structures across the entire precursor concentration range. This behaviour is consistent with the higher activation energy required for ZnO nucleation in these solvents, which favours lateral rather than perpendicular growth [36]. GIXRD patterns of coatings deposited from ethanolic mixtures aligned with the observed trends in substrate coverage and preferential growth as a function of precursor concentration. The sample prepared using a 0.2 M ethanolic solution exhibited an enhanced (101) plane reflection, which correlates with the formation of blade-like rod tips due to the lower surface tension of alcohols favouring activation {10 n} planes [40]. Similarly, the GIXRD pattern of the sample prepared from an IPA solution confirmed [001] preferential growth, in agreement with the rod-like morphology. In contrast, low crystallinity was detected in the film prepared from MeOH, while no preferential *c*-axis orientation was observed for the film prepared from Me₂CO precursor solution (Fig. 5g).

In summary, AACVD using ethanolic ZnCl₂ solutions proved to be a highly controllable method for producing homogeneous ZnO NR film coatings with excellent surface coverage and well-defined NRs. This approach facilitated the direct formation of crystalline coatings over large areas without the need for organic surfactants or additional post-processing steps, highlighting its potential for scalability. A comprehensive summary of rod/NSs morphology, rod width, and surface coverage for all samples is provided in Table S3 (Supporting Information). Top-view and cross-sectional SEM images illustrating surface coverage and film thickness are provided in Figures S1 and S2 (Supporting Information). Selected coatings showing homogeneous coverage, directional *c*-axis growth, columnar (rod/blade) morphology, and sub-100 nm widths – characteristics indicative of highly active NSs surfaces – were subjected to optical analysis and antiviral testing.

3.2. Optical analysis

The optical properties of the synthesised ZnO NRs were evaluated using UV-Visible spectroscopy in the 300–1200 nm range. All as-synthesised film coatings showed optical transparency in the visible range. However, for optical analysis, we selected ZnO film coatings that demonstrated preferential [001] growth, NR-like morphology with well-aligned structures, and good surface coverage. The chosen coatings – DropCast + HT (0.05 M), AACVD/EtOH (0.1 M) and AACVD/EtOH (0.2 M) – were optically transparent and displayed an absorption edge

centred around 380 nm (Fig. 6), in agreement with a ~3.3 eV bandgap calculated using Tauc's formula for a direct-bandgap semiconductor (inset) [42,43]. While the AACVD-derived samples showed a typical optical response, the DropCast + HT (0.05 M) sample featured a secondary blue-shifted bandgap near 3.7 eV, indicative of an amorphous ZnO contribution [41]. This reduced crystallinity is likely due to the presence of residual impurities during NR growth. Previous studies have reported similar optical characteristics in ZnO film coatings synthesised from zinc acetates/acetonates, where partial amorphous phases persist at 400 °C due to the formation of graphitic clusters within the oxide structure, which come from the thermal decomposition of precursors [41]. The observed loss of crystallinity in DropCast + HT samples can be attributed to carbon incorporation during growth at suboptimal decarbonisation temperatures, whereas AACVD-grown coatings, prepared from a carbon-free precursor, exhibit full crystallinity.

Although this interpretation may appear inconsistent with crystallinity indicators from GIXRD spectra (see Figs. 4f and 5g), a direct comparison requires caution, as these spectra were obtained from NS

Fig. 6. Absorbance in the visible range and Tauc plot [42] (inset) of selected ZnO NSs thin film coatings with rod-like nanostructures. Dotted black line represents the absorbance of the glass substrate, the red arrows indicate the bandgap of crystalline ZnO and the orange arrow indicates the bandgap of amorphous ZnO [41]. The bandgap of glass (3.9 eV) is not represented for clarity.

films of varying thicknesses (see Figs. S1 and S2 in Supporting information). An in-depth discussion on the material-centred reasons why thickness is not the controlling parameter in this case is also provided in Supporting Information. Top-view SEM micrographs of the selected samples revealed that the glass substrate remained visible in AACVD-derived coatings (Fig. 5), whereas it is completely obscured in DropCast + HT samples, indicating that the latter is significantly thicker. This is consistent with their higher signal-to-noise ratio observed in GIXRD measurements.

3.3. Photocatalytic and antiviral testing

The antiviral performance of the three NSs ZnO film coatings was assessed by evaluating the inactivation kinetics of the MS2 bacteriophage under ambient white light illumination (~1000 lux). The samples were exposed for up to 2 h following the protocol described in the experimental section. These samples were also illuminated during 3 h, achieving a similar inactivation efficiency. Detailed plots are provided in the Supporting Information (Fig. 4S).

Among the tested samples, ZnO NRs film coatings fabricated via AACVD exhibited the highest antiviral efficiency, achieving ≈ 4 -log (99.99 %) MS2 bacteriophage inactivation after 2 h of exposure (Fig. 7). In contrast, the best performing drop-cast/hydrothermal coatings produced only ≈ 2 -log reductions under identical conditions, while sol-gel-based films displayed negligible activity. To exclude dark (non-photocatalytic) inactivation mechanisms, dark controls were performed in parallel using the same ISO 18071:2016 covered-droplet geometry (25 μ L droplet covered with a 1×1 cm² glass slide) and the same exposure time but without illumination; these controls showed negligible MS2 inactivation (Figure S5). These results clearly indicate that the synthesis route governs not only the morphology and crystallinity of the ZnO films but also their photocatalytic efficiency and antiviral capability. Additionally, the AACVD ZnO NRs coatings maintained their macroscopic integrity and adhesion after repeated antiviral tests (three consecutive cycles), showing no visible delamination or measurable loss of performance.

Since MS2 inactivation does not occur in solution, it is expected to

Fig. 7. Viable counts of bacteriophage MS2 after exposure to standard laboratory white light (1000 lux) on borosilicate substrates (1 cm²) coated with NSs ZnO film coatings produced by wet chemistry methods (DropCast + HT 0.05 M) and aerosol-assisted chemical vapour deposition (AACVD/EtOH 0.1 M and AACVD/EtOH 0.2 M). \star indicates that the viable count was below the detection limit of 100 PFU/mL. The control is a blank borosilicate piece (1 cm²).

occur only via production of ROS. Nanosizing of ZnO increases the effective surface area, light absorption, and charge separation [44,45], thereby increasing production of ROS. Upon white light illumination, ZnO generates electron-hole (e^-/h^+) that migrate to the surface to react with adsorbed water and oxygen molecules, forming ROS such as hydroxyl radicals (\bullet OH), superoxide anions ($O_2^{\bullet-}$), hydroperoxyl radicals (HO_2^{\bullet}), and hydrogen peroxide (H_2O_2) [46,47]. These species are well known in photocatalytic oxidation processes and environmental remediation for their high oxidative potency, and similar ROS mechanisms have been invoked in antiviral nanomaterials [48–50]. The key reactions can be summarised as:

The generated ROS can induce oxidative damage to viral proteins, lipids, and nucleic acids, compromising virus integrity and infectivity. To exclude the possibility that Zn²⁺ leaching contributed to viral inactivation, the post-exposure droplets were analysed by ICP-OES using a semi-quantitative mode. The measured Zn²⁺ concentrations for AACVD/EtOH (0.2 M), AACVD/EtOH (0.1 M) and DropCast + HT (0.05 M) were 0.03, 0.17 and 0.41 mg·L⁻¹ (≈ 0.46 , 2.60 and 6.27 μ M, respectively). These values are one to two orders of magnitude below Zn²⁺ concentrations reported to inhibit viral replication or cause direct virucidal effects (typically \geq tens of μ M) [51,52]. Moreover, dark controls performed in the same covered-droplet geometry (identical droplets on coated samples kept in the dark for 2 h) showed no detectable MS2 inactivation. We note that the sample exhibiting the highest measured Zn²⁺ concentration (0.41 mg·L⁻¹) displayed no detectable antiviral activity under the same white light conditions. This observation demonstrates that Zn²⁺ release does not drive the antiviral effect, if ionic Zn were the main cause, the sample with the highest Zn should have shown the greatest activity. Consequently, the combined dataset – (i) very low Zn²⁺ in active samples, (ii) higher Zn²⁺ in a non-active sample, and (iii) absence of activity in dark controls – supports the assignment of photocatalytically generated ROS at the ZnO surface as the primary antiviral mechanism under indoor white light. We have added the ICP-OES values and the activity outcome for each sample to Table S5 (Supporting Information) for transparency.

The markedly higher antiviral activity observed for AACVD-grown ZnO NRs coatings can be rationalised in terms of their distinctive structural and physicochemical features. The AACVD process yields highly crystalline, phase-pure ZnO NRs with strong [001] orientation and homogeneous surface coverage, as well as firm adhesion to the substrate [53]. On the contrary, ZnO coatings prepared through wet-chemistry approaches suffer from incorporation of non-volatile carbon-based by-products from organometallic precursors during synthesis, which leads to partial amorphous character and a pronounced bandgap blue-shift (Fig. 6). The lack of organic by-products during vapour-phase growth in AACVD minimises trap states and non-radiative recombination centres, allowing photogenerated charge carriers to persist longer and participate in redox reactions at the surface. The resulting dense and well-adhered NR arrays provide an extended active area and enhanced light scattering, both of which favour photon absorption and ROS generation [54]. Moreover, the sharp absorption edge and lower Urbach energy of the AACVD coatings, indicative of fewer sub-bandgap states, enable more efficient utilisation of visible photons under indoor illumination [55]. These structural and optical attributes collectively promote higher interfacial ROS fluxes, which oxidatively disrupt viral capsid proteins and nucleic acids, leading to faster inactivation kinetics.

To place our findings in context, we compared the antiviral performance of the AACVD ZnO NR coatings (≈ 4 -log MS2 inactivation in 2 h under room white light ~ 1000 lux) with representative photocatalytic thin film systems reported in the literature. These comparisons highlight differences in materials, light conditions, test geometries, and antiviral performance, and underscore the novelty of our approach. A summary of representative antiviral photocatalytic coatings, together with our AACVD ZnO NR film coating, is presented in Table S4 of the Supporting Information.

Nakano *et al* [56], demonstrated that TiO₂ thin films achieved ≈ 4 -log influenza virus inactivation under low-intensity UVA irradiation, confirming that thin films can in principle deliver high log reductions, albeit under UV rather than visible light. In a more directly comparable regime, a Cu_xO/TiO₂ composite coating achieved ≈ 4 -log SARS-CoV-2 inactivation under ~ 1000 lux visible light within 2 h, closely matching the illumination conditions used in this study [57]. This shows that composite or heterostructure strategies can perform effectively under indoor lighting, at the cost of increased material complexity. In contrast, ZnO-based particle/acrylic binder coatings used against SARS-CoV-2, achieved $> 99\%$ (≈ 2 log) inactivation after 24 h under ambient light, indicating much slower kinetics [58]. More recently, high-touch composite coatings have demonstrated faster virus inactivation through engineered surfaces and additives under visible light, but these typically require more elaborate fabrication procedures [27]. Overall, while many reported systems achieve effective antiviral activity, they often rely on UV or high-energy illumination, doped or composite materials, or immersion/flow geometries. In contrast, our ZnO NR film coatings achieve multi-log MS2 inactivation on firmly adhered, single-step coatings under low-intensity indoor white light, without the need for dopants or heterostructures. This favourable combination of performance, simplicity, and compatibility with indoor lighting distinguishes our approach from most literature examples.

4. Conclusions

This work demonstrates that the synthesis route exerts a crucial influence on the structural, optical, and photocatalytic properties of ZnO NRs film coatings, which directly determine their antiviral efficiency under indoor white light illumination. Comparative evaluation of solution-based and vapour-phase deposition techniques revealed that AACVD produced ZnO films with the most favourable combination of structural and functional properties. The AACVD-grown coatings consisted of densely packed, vertically aligned, and highly crystalline ZnO NRs exhibiting [001] orientation and phase purity, without the need for seeding layers or surfactants. In contrast, drop-cast and hydrothermally treated coatings presented partial amorphous character and carbon contamination, which induced a blue-shift in optical absorption and reduced photocatalytic activity.

The structural advantages of AACVD-grown coatings translated directly into superior photocatalytic performance. They achieved ≈ 4 -log (99.99%) MS2 bacteriophage inactivation after 2 h of exposure to standard white light, whereas the best performing solution-processed films reached only ≈ 2 -log reductions under identical conditions. Dark controls confirmed that viral inactivation occurred exclusively under illumination, evidencing a light-dependent photocatalytic process. ICP-OES analyses revealed only trace Zn²⁺ release (≤ 0.41 mg•L⁻¹, < 7 μ M), far below concentrations known to cause antiviral effects. Furthermore, the sample with the highest Zn²⁺ leaching exhibited no antiviral activity, demonstrating that Zn²⁺ dissolution is not responsible for viral inactivation. These observations, together with the absence of activity in the dark, confirm that the antiviral effect originates from photocatalytically generated ROS (\bullet OH, O₂[•], HO₂[•], and H₂O₂) produced at the ZnO surface under white light excitation.

Beyond their functional performance, the AACVD coatings exhibited excellent mechanical robustness and retained full activity after multiple antiviral test cycles. From a processing perspective, AACVD offers

significant advantages: i) it operates as a single-step, ii) scalable deposition process, iii) moderate substrate temperature (~ 400 °C), iv) and short reaction times (< 30 min). The method also minimises waste through efficient precursor consumption and the containment of gaseous by-products, ensuring good environmental compatibility.

Overall, this study identifies AACVD as a powerful, sustainable route for the production of high-quality ZnO NRs coatings that combine reproducible structure, strong adhesion, and robust antiviral photocatalytic performance. Their proven activity under standard indoor white light conditions and compatibility with large-area deposition highlight their potential for practical integration onto high-touch surfaces – such as hospital equipment, food-processing environments, transport interior, and household appliances – to provide continuous, passive viral deactivation, without chemical disinfectants or UV radiation.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Deyna I. de la Fuente Rodríguez: Validation, Investigation, Formal analysis. **Marugán Aguado Javier:** Writing – review & editing, Visualization, Validation, Methodology, Formal analysis, Conceptualization. **Sotelo-Vázquez Carlos:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Visualization, Validation, Project administration, Methodology, Investigation, Funding acquisition, Formal analysis, Data curation, Conceptualization. **Clara Sanchez-Perez:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Visualization, Validation, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Data curation, Conceptualization.

Declaration of Competing Interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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Appendix A. Supporting information

Supplementary data associated with this article can be found in the online version at [doi:10.1016/j.jece.2025.120195](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jece.2025.120195).

Data availability

Data will be made available on request.

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